

01

SPECIAL
ISSUE

STRUCTURAL TREATMENTS ON DOUBLE-SIDED PAINTINGS

CONSERVING CANVAS

Structural
treatments
on double-sided
paintings

CENTRO
CONSERVAZIONE
RESTAURO
LA VENARIA REALE

Getty
Foundation

STRUCTURAL TREATMENTS ON DOUBLE-SIDED PAINTINGS

Case-studies and professional experiences on double-sided paintings (18 November 2020) and Expert meeting (23, 24, 25 November 2020)
Proceedings

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On the cover: Giulio Cesare Procaccini, *Virgin and Child, St. Ambrose, St. Charles Borromeo and angels* (front); *Virgin and Child, St. John, St. Peter and angels* (back), Milan, Pinacoteca di Brera, detail of the back during the conservation treatment.

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INSTITUTIONAL INTRODUCTIONS

The “Structural treatments on double-sided paintings” project is part of the “Conserving Canvas” initiative funded by the Getty Foundation. By joining this Programme, we have drawn on important testimonies from the highly qualified and prestigious museums, research centres and cultural institutions that preceded us. We are particularly honoured by this great opportunity offered to us by the Getty Foundation, which we sincerely thank.

The proposed training project was developed starting from an extremely complex case study: the conservation treatment of a banner painted on both sides by Giulio Cesare Procaccini owned by the Pinacoteca di Brera. Once underway, the collaboration was an opportunity to enjoy a new synergy between our institutions, and I must thank Director Bradburne and all the staff of the Museum for having believed in this project.

A special thanks goes to all the conservators and professionals who, together with us, have taken up a small challenge offered by digital technology: opening these events up to our entire scientific community, and welcoming those who would otherwise have been excluded. For this I thank Matteo Rossi Doria who collaborated in building this important network of relationships and, first and foremost, the Director of our Laboratories, Michela Cardinali, for the foresight shown and for being the driver and beating heart of this project.

Last but not least, I would like to thank the whole community of conservators, professionals and students who, together with us, have followed the Project, and whose active and numerous attendance confirms how worthwhile and valid the new path that the Centre has chosen to take is.

Stefano Trucco

President - Centro Conservazione e Restauro “La Venaria Reale”

The “Structural treatments on double-sided paintings” project, and in general the entire programme supported by the Getty Foundation, is undoubtedly the most important opportunity we have had to join the international conservation community. The topic of our project, which focuses on the study and conservation of double-sided paintings, came out from a Master’s Thesis in Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage, run in agreement with the University of Turin: this aspect is not secondary; indeed it shows just how important the link between research and training is.

Thanks to the “Conserving Canvas” initiative, it was possible to continue and deepen our studies and to involve experts from near and far: we have acquired new knowledge, but also new issues to address, discovering many more questions than we could ever have imagined. Which is why we hope that the objectives of the programme, successfully achieved, will become the starting point for a new research.

I would like to express my gratitude to the colleagues and professionals who have taken up this challenge. The goal of the Centre for the next few years will be to encourage the development of technical, scientific and historical research applied to the conservation of cultural heritage.

And I would like to add, as an art historian, that I am extremely pleased and above all very honoured to find in this publication such a qualified group of researchers and experts in the restoration of paintings.

Sara Abram

Secretary General - Centro Conservazione e Restauro “La Venaria Reale”

In late 2019, the Getty Foundation awarded a Conserving Canvas grant to the Centro per la Conservazione ed il Restauro dei Beni Culturali “La Venaria Reale” in Torino, for training and treatment related to *Virgin with Child, Saints, and Angels* by Giulio Cesare Procaccini from the collection of the Pinacoteca di Brera. This large, painted banner presents complex conservation challenges because of the fragile nature of the canvas that sits “sandwiched” between two painted sides and is, therefore, relatively inaccessible. The team of experts at the Centre was well aware of these challenges and, as part of the grant project, had planned an international experts meeting with art historians, conservators, and scientists to discuss the painting and possible treatment options. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, however, the in-person expert meetings were diverted to the online realm. The Conserving Canvas experts meeting organized by the Centre marks the beginning of an important and open dialogue about the structural conservation of double-sided canvas paintings. Over a four-day period from November 18-25, 2020, Italian specialists discussed a range of conservation approaches with their colleagues from around the globe in front of an international audience. The result, presented in this publication, not only demonstrates the thoughtful approach of the Centre’s conservation team to preserving Procaccini’s painting, but also proves a remarkable level of commitment by the international conservation community. Knowledge sharing is a key strategy of the Foundation’s Conserving Canvas grant initiative, and conservation professionals worldwide have matched our commitment as generous thought partners.

Conserving Canvas is an international grant initiative of the Getty Foundation in Los Angeles focused on improving the conservation of paintings on canvas. Artists began to use canvas supports during the 15th century in Europe, and the material quickly grew in popularity. For centuries, it was common practice to protect canvas paintings by backing or lining them with another canvas, to create a moisture barrier and provide greater structural integrity. Conserving Canvas aims to ensure that conservators remain fully prepared to care for these important works of art through a combination of training activities and information dissemination.

We are grateful to the Centro per la Conservazione ed il Restauro dei Beni Culturali “La Venaria Reale” for having organized the experts meeting and, in particular we want to thank Director Michela Cardinali and her fabulous interdisciplinary team of experts for so effortlessly having transitioned the meeting and its rich content to an online environment. Our gratitude also goes out to Pinacoteca di Brera Director James Bradburne and to his colleagues Francesca Debolini and Andrea Carini for their unwavering support for the project. The fact that so many Italian and international colleagues joined the meeting, is testimony to how much the conservation field has advanced, and to how much this community values the sharing of information.

Antoine Wilmering

Senior Program Officer - The Getty Foundation

FOREWORDS

Conservation: getting out of the attic

Ever since the reform of the Ministry of Cultural Heritage in 2014, a certain tension has existed between the idea of conservation, the traditional mission of the Ministry since its inception in 1974, and that of valorization, seen as the new mission promoted by the Minister Dario Franceschini. In the controversy which plagued the early years of the reforms, the Pinacoteca di Brera was often used as an example of the dangers of abandoning conservation to embrace valorization, whereby the museum's mission consisted of marketing, increasing visitors and revenue, and in which the artworks would be sacrificed on the altar of ruthless capitalism. While the debate might have laid emphasis on the possible dangers of a market-based museum mission, Brera was arguably the least suitable example to use and demonize. Indeed, since 2015, the Pinacoteca has turned its back on tourism, with its concomitant goal of increasing footfall and visitor revenues at any cost, and has instead put its permanent collection at the centre, rearranging the collections and refusing to organize temporary exhibitions. Paradoxically, at least for those who mistakenly think in terms of a continuum where conservation is on the one side and valorization is on the other, and every move towards one means an estrangement from the other, Brera has combined the two, and has invested substantially more in conservation – and its valorization – than in earlier decades. Conservation is seen as the first step of valorization, a necessary but far from self-sufficient condition to create new value for the public with the permanent collections kept by the State in the name of the community. Recalling the radical mission of the first public museums forged by the French Revolution, and the mission of Italian museums before the creation of the Ministry of Cultural Heritage, conservation is the first step in any popular education programme. The museum is a community's "manor house", a keeper of collective memories to encourage reflection on the future, to avoid citizens being reduced to mere voters, and their rich collective identity reduced to that of their consumption choices.

Conservation is fundamental to the work of museums, and conservators are frequently its unsung heroes. This is not the case with Brera. Since 2008, the Pinacoteca has an open conservation laboratory designed by Ettore Sottsass, and since 2015 this has played an important role in its strategy to create an "open museum", where the entire range of the museum's work (not just the works of art exhibited) is made visible to the public. Open restoration plays an important role in the identity of the museum and major works have been restored *in situ*. In 2018, thanks to funds from the Bank of America Merrill Lynch, our large Tiepolo painting was restored openly, a process requiring more than six months of work. More recently, a second open conservation laboratory was created specifically to restore Gerolamo Genga's massive panel, with the support of two private sponsors. After two shutdowns due to the current pandemic, the Brera's work moved online, and restoration has become an important focus of the museum's online channels and website, as well as a regularly feature on *Brera On Air*.

Restoration is therefore an important part of the museum's work, and the conservators are its stars. Given the greater visibility of their activity, restoration is also a valorization and conveys the message that a museum is much more than just exhibitions. In the community's "manor house" we must first take care of the artworks, before being able to make them available to the widest possible audience. Before we can sit on chairs they need to be mended, just as memories need to be preserved if we want to carry them with us from the past to the present in order to build our future.

James Bradburne

Director - Pinacoteca di Brera

The “Structural treatments on double-sided paintings” training project. Digital innovation and a method for technical-scientific development

The training project “Structural treatments on double-sided paintings” represents a first, multi-faceted and informed experience of the digital transformation process which the Centro Conservazione e Restauro (CCR) began to use starting from spring 2020. The Project, presented to the Getty Foundation as part of the “Conserving Canvas” initiative in 2019, aims to promote the transmission of skills and knowledge related to the technical issues of structural treatment and stretching of double-sided paintings. In fact, since 2018, the ongoing recovery of an extremely complex case, the banner painted on both sides by Giulio Cesare Procaccini from the Pinacoteca di Brera, had brought these issues to our attention along with an evident need for further studies and discussions with experts in the field. To this end, as a part of the project, a course of study and training was developed at an international level, through technical investigations within the CCR and the conservation laboratories. In fact, in its initial version, the project envisaged activities and operational phases in person, in line with the usual standards for our professional community. In the first months of the Covid-19 lockdown, at a time of great uncertainty about the future, we felt, deeply and personally, the difficulties due to the distances and isolation imposed by the pandemic. Faced with this situation, in order to bring our professional community closer together while continuing to develop the themes dearest to our work, namely, the conservation of our cultural heritage in conjunction with training, we soon realized that we needed to take a step forward and change our point of view and habits. For this reason, in sessions to compare notes and have discussions with the team of professionals involved, we redesigned the project to make it more suitable to respond to the new historical contingency. Thanks to its digital transformation, the project has been integrated with a series of actions aimed at accessibility, participation, and intercultural integration. The response received was as unexpected as it was surprising: the need for discussion and the possibility of swapping opinions emerged in our community, the need to share experiences and information, to move forward and develop new, increasingly specialized skills, overcoming some of the existing barriers and limitations. In this sense, the change, initially difficult and repulsive, generated new possibilities for development and regenerated consolidated working methods. We refreshed and supplemented the training program with various online events for a total of around 12 hours of live broadcasts, eventually watched by 1,200 subscribers from 54 countries. The project as a whole is divided into several phases:

1. Preliminary bibliographic research dedicated to similar case studies carried out nationally and internationally (2020);
2. Presentation of some of the case studies collected, for the most part an expression of how things stand in Italy (18 November 2020);
3. Expert Meeting: 3 meetings between experts in the field dedicated to a scientific discussion on the two focus topics of the project and on the case study of the Procaccini banner (23, 24, 25 November 2020);

4. Two workshops aimed at 6 mid-career conservators selected through an international Call (please see the report by Sara Aveni in this same volume). As will be explained in greater detail in the following pages, the feedback received from this experience has offered an important contribution to the strategic orientation of the CCR towards a new method of sharing and training, based on accessibility, inclusion, and sustainability. As part of the initiatives to disseminate the project results, this digital publication, also available on the CCR website, sets out to systematize and share the contents of our experience, to reorganize and further investigate the contributions presented by all the experts involved during the digital events. In particular, in the publication, it will be possible to take a closer look at the different topics dealt with during the “live” days: from the Italian case studies dedicated to the theme of double-sided paintings, to the repairing of tears, the mechanical properties of paintings, and the stretching systems. The results obtained from this experience, despite the depressing period in which it developed, encouraged the team from the Advanced Training School to promote the digital transformation process which is gradually involving the whole of the CCR. Indeed, from the end of 2021, innovative new activities will be proposed to enjoy intercultural experiences and inhabit the digital environment in an informed, sustainable and accessible way, with an inclusive approach taking in the entire conservation community. The “Structural treatments on double-sided paintings” project has actually allowed the start of this process of change and the development of our training, teaching and fruition activities in a new digital key. I must thank the Getty Foundation for the support and openness with which it welcomed the development proposals and the changes made by the CCR team during the course of the work¹.

Michela Cardinali

Conservation Laboratories and School of Advanced Training Director - Centro Conservazione e Restauro “La Venaria Reale”

¹ Special thanks must go to the project team, because ‘special’ describes their work and the contribution offered at every stage of developing this experience, and in particular to: Lara Coniglio, Marianna Ferrero, Matteo Rossi Doria, Bernadette Ventura, Sara Aveni, Alessandro Ventrice, Cosimo Morleo and Maria Elena Delia, Lorenza Ghionna, and Stefania De Blasi.

PART 1

**CASE STUDIES
PRESENTATION
AND
PROFESSIONAL
EXPERIENCES ON
DOUBLE-SIDED
PAINTINGS**

Michela Cardinali

Conservation Labs and
School of Advanced Training
Director, CCR “La Venaria
Reale”

Case studies presentation and professional experiences on double-sided paintings. An overview of Italian expertise

The launch of the “Structural treatments on double-sided paintings” project involved a first phase of research to identify case studies comparable to the banner of Giulio Cesare Procaccini from a historical-artistic and conservation point of view, both in Italy and abroad. The main objective of the preliminary screening was to summarize the current situation when it comes to the treatment of double-sided paintings on canvas, with particular reference to the repairing of tears in the textile support and the stretching of the artwork.

Procaccini’s banner represents a very particular case study from a technical point of view due to its characteristics and behaviour, with similarities to both paintings on canvas and banners painted on other kinds of textile support. As a result, it has been difficult to find a case exactly comparable to ours, due to the type of artwork and the serious nature of the conservation problems to be dealt with. Despite this, the preliminary research phase¹ allowed us to become acquainted with other experiences and understand how this kind of artwork has been studied and restored in other contexts and countries. To begin with, the available bibliography was screened, as exhaustively as possible, but somewhat hampered by the closure of archives and libraries during the 2020 Covid-19 lockdown.

On the basis of the data collected, various institutions were then contacted which, in various capacities, would be able to support our research: museums and organizations which had already participated in the Getty Foundation’s “Conserving Canvas” initiative; in general, museums which keep double-

sided banners or paintings, heritage protection institutions which could point us to artworks in Italy, restoration centres and laboratories that have already carried out complex interventions on double-sided paintings, both in Italy and abroad. In order to organize the information in a systematic way, we prepared a form with the essential data on the works and the interventions carried out, to be shared with the bodies/professionals concerned and to be made available also on the CCR website.

The collaboration with other institutions which had participated in the Conserving Canvas Initiative², such as the SRAL, the Dallas Museum of Art, the Statens Historiska Museer, to name but a few, proved extremely fruitful. These organizations supported us in the research, the sharing of information, bibliographic resources, and contacts with other colleagues who have worked on the same problems. This first phase of work, in addition to strengthening our network, allowed us to make our project known and to lay the foundations for the Expert Meetings held in November 2020. An analysis of the various experiences enabled us to collect a good number of case studies and to obtain a rather broad mapping of the conservation issues and problems associated with double-sided paintings.

In this phase of understanding and verifying the current thinking on the subject, the relevance of the studies and conservation activities conducted in Italy led to the idea of presenting an overview of the Italian experience in caring for a heritage which our country is particularly rich in. A webinar entitled “Case studies and professional experiences on double-sided paintings” was therefore organized on 18 November 2020; an integrated event connected to the Expert Meetings of 23-25 November 2020. The study day included 4 live talks and 9 videos dedicated to two main thematic areas: repair of lacerations and the stretching of double-sided paintings and banners. These presentations were associated with an interactive chat session for sharing and listening, managed by a moderator who collected the questions and dealt with the answers. The event was followed by over 600 professionals, scholars, or people interested in the experiences being presented. The important result obtained during the event and the numerous examples of feedback received afterwards led

us to compile the systematic and complete collection of the various contributions now being presented in this volume. On this occasion what emerged was the need of our scientific community to enter into relationships, to get to know and share experiences, and to constantly update their professional pursuit with other points of view. As a part of this project, the Centre's working group tried to respond to this need, bridging the gaps that unexpectedly appeared during the lockdown.

This approach, especially in a time of crisis and change like the one we are living through, seeks to generate new scientific vigour and new development opportunities for the discipline of the conservation of cultural property.

¹ Conducted by Sara Aveni and Caterina Fontana.

² We would like to thank Laura Eva Hartman (Dallas Museum of Art), Ann-Cathrin Rothlind and Annika Williams (Statens Historiska Museer), Elise Effmann Clifford and Sarah Kleiner (The Fine Arts Museum of San Francisco), Shawn Digney-Peer (The Metropolitan Museum of Art), Kate Seymour (SRAL), Simone Mancini (The National Gallery of Ireland), Livia Depuydt (KIK-IRPA), Johanna Nilsson (Armémuseum), Emmy de Groot (University of Amsterdam) for sharing references and information on past treatments. To mention just a few of the suggested publications: L. Waters, *Tear Repair of Cotton Canvas: A variation of the Heiber Technique*, WAAC Newsletter, Vol. 28, no. 2, May 2006; S. Beiner-Büth, S. Beckmann, *Faserbei zur Schließung klaffender Risse Ein Werkstattbericht*,

VDR Beitrage, 2007; J.N. Richardson, *The Brotherhood of Saint Leonard and Saint Francis: Banners, Sacred Topography and Confraternal Identity in Assisi*, Association of Art Historians 2011; *Setting the Scene: European painted cloths from the fourteenth to the twenty-first century*, Edited by N. Costaras, C. Young, Archetype Publications Ltd, October 2013; L.E. Hartman, *When the Dog Bites: Tear Mending a Large Steven Parrino Painting following a Dog Attack*, AIC Painting Speciality Group Postprints, 30, 2017, pp. 55-68. In addition to the authors who contributed to this publication, we would like to thank: Maria Consiglia Stile for the information on the treatment conducted on the double-sided painting attributed to Bartolomeo Schedoni, and Tiziana Monacelli for information on the banner from Gubbio attributed to Raphael and Evangelista da Pian di Meleto (?).

PART 1

Session 1

Tear mending on double-sided paintings

24. Matteo da Gualdo, general, back, after the restoration treatment.

the two canvases from the frame/stretcher, had lined both of them because they were torn and incomplete, and had nailed them back onto the original frame/stretcher, blocking them with two thin strips of wood subsequently painted. Our own intervention, carried out in 2002-2003, was therefore limited to operations of a substantially aesthetic nature (fig. 24).

PART 1

Session 2

Mechanical properties and stretching of double-sided paintings

The supports for double-sided paintings

THE USE OF TENSION FOR DOUBLE-SIDED PAINTINGS

Old masters' paintings were often sized and prepared on the same stretcher they were painted on, as the procedure locks the threads of the canvas, which are often found draped over the tacks: canvas was nailed in place and then sized with a water solution of animal glue. Water caused canvas shrinkage, while the swollen twisted yarns found a better organization through creep and slippage of the fibers. When the water evaporated, canvas dimensions were permanently increased, but glue contraction restored canvas tension on the stretcher. Glue sizing made the canvas a suitable support for painting also because it increased the elastic modulus of the fabric, now transformed in a composite material, while locking and protecting the threads. Glue sizing was a structural requirement also for double-sided paintings and banners. In fig.1 the graph illustrates the tension build-up in warp and weft of a canvas prepared with the described procedure. The average values of the test¹ show that a linen canvas, starting from the tension of 1,8 N/cm, when wet with a solution of animal glue, experiences a sudden increase of tension, up to 3,0 N/cm. As water evaporates, tension drops to 0,4 N/cm, rising again to 2,1 N/cm when glue reaches equilibrium with environmental humidity at 50% RH.

When environmental moisture is high, expansion of glue causes a reduction of tension on the painting, as the canvas is deprived of the tension provided by the glue; tension reduction may become partially compensated by the expansion of the wooden stretcher; extremely high RH causes a new contraction of the canvas, however this is unlikely to

1. The time plot of biaxial tension of samples of linen canvas stretched at 2 N/cm and then sized with animal glue at 50% RH. Samples recovered initial tension, although the canvas has become elongated (@ A. Iaccarino Idelson and M. Sanchez).

2. Checking painting tension, above the limit of 2-2,5 N/cm its ability to resist deformation tends to stabilize.

cause damage because it starts from a relatively low tension. Low RH sees glue contraction and tension rises up to forces that can easily cause the distortion of a wooden stretcher in very dry environments. Still, within “normal” RH fluctuations (approx. 30%-80%) the animal glue-controlled equilibrium² is relatively stable. Ageing of the glue layers causes embrittlement and cracking, leading to a reduction of the painting’s ability to recover tension with cycling RH. This is likely to be the main reason why “the practice of lining evolved towards the end of the 17th century, roughly 150 years after the introduction of oil painting on canvas technique” [Percival Prescott, 2003]. With key expansion stretchers, introduced around 1750 [Pernety, 1757], stretcher bars could move away from the center, thus increasing tension. Still, expansion caused overstretching of the canvas in the corner areas, because canvas was still fixed on the perimeter as it had always been. Corner expansion made a radical change in paintings’ mechanics, causing the insurgence of a new class of damages.

3. Edge of stretcher equipped with strips rolling on ball bearings to reduce friction.

Following the desire to correct the problems related to the use of movable keys, the first patents of stretchers with corner springs in place of the keys appeared on the US market in the mid 19th century. But spring-loaded corner expansion proved to be very dangerous: hidden in the stretcher bars, springs need to be small and to provide a great amount of expansion force to overcome the high friction in the stretcher corners. For this reason, relaxation cycles allow the opening of the stretcher, but the contraction of the painting materials is neither able to exceed friction nor to compress the springs. Resulting stress concentrations exceed the painting's yield and failure points. Consequences soon proved to be dramatic enough to favor constructions that entailed less friction and softer springs, especially for the more fragile double-sided paintings, and the Starofix is a good example [Bonetti, 1999].

In 1953, at the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro in Rome, a new stretcher design was devised, which freed the painting from tacks or staples and allowed it to move on the perimeter being connected to springs placed on the reverse. The method was extensively used over a decade, for a large number of canvas paintings. The first to be published were the two Caravaggio masterpieces in St. John's co-Cathedral in la Valletta [Carità, 1957]. Since then, the choice of the springs, and that of the force they should produce to equilibrate the painting's cycling dimensional variations, has become a relevant subject. Carità published [Carità, 1955] the force used for tensioning detached wall paintings (1,36 N/cm) when

responding to critics stating that strong tension may induce new crack formation. Regarding canvas paintings, he stated that they could withstand very high forces (in the range of 18 N/cm), but we should keep in mind that at that time a stiff paste lining with two superposed linen canvases was the rule. When the St. Gerome came back from Valletta for a new treatment at the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro in 1989, the subject was updated and the value of tension was lowered (6 N/cm) along with that of the elastic constant of the springs [Accardo, 1991].

In 1993 a painting (similar in dimensions and lining to the St. Gerome) was satisfactorily stretched with a lower tension (2,6 N/cm) using its original strainer with the addition of sliding profiles and springs on the reverse [Iaccarino, 1996]. Between 2000 and 2003, research was carried out to obtain objective data for the determination of a correct value of tension for lined and unlined paintings. A great wealth of information was collected on the behavior of 9 paintings, and the existence of a threshold of maximum useful tension was found. When the hands of the conservator impose a pressure on the painting to check its tension, they will find that by increasing tension more than 2-2,5 N/cm, the paintings ability to resist deformation tends to stabilize, as shown in fig. 2 [Iaccarino, 2004]. This was interestingly confirmed by a survey carried out by Equilibrarte in 2005 on a sample of 106 senior Italian conservators, who were asked to choose tension for the same mockup painting: the average value was 1,8 N/cm. Since 2002, Equilibrarte has stretched several hundreds of paintings using the forces described as follows:

- fragile leather or silk artifacts: 0.02 – 0.8 N/cm
- unlined paintings: 0.8 – 1.6 N/cm
- lined paintings: 1.4 – 2.4 N/cm
- heavy ceiling paintings: up to 3,2 N/cm

Dimensions of the painting do not influence the choice of tension because the force is measured as a function of the unity of length of the perimeter: a large painting will be stretched with a similar force to that used for a small one. The characteristics that most influence the need for tension are the elastic modulus, the thickness and the weight/m² of the painting. As most mechanical measures are not easy to perform on a real painting, its weight makes a good overall

4. A double-sided silk banner by Sodoma (16th century) floating on very soft springs with no friction.

indicator. Part of the force is absorbed by the friction on the sliding perimeter. To be more precise, friction requires the painting to develop a force that is strong enough to overcome a threshold, making the system work discontinuously. Therefore, when the painting produces a small variation of tension, it will need to reach a certain build-up to equilibrate with springs. The value of friction force has been measured at approx. 0,3 N/cm for sliding profiles that reduce friction with Teflon or high-density Polyethylene. An extremely small force, which can be further reduced with the introduction of rolling profiles on ball bearings (fig. 3). For double-sided paintings, the problem is solved even more efficiently, as the painting is suspended in a frame and has no friction on fixed elements (fig. 4).

A banner used in a procession hanging from its horizontal pole moves in the air, and dangerous stresses are limited to the presence of wind or similar forces. When stretched for

exhibition in a museum, allowing observation from both sides, a banner faces dangers connected to air pressure that single-sided paintings do not normally face as their backsides are usually placed against a wall. Stress release can be granted if springs allow displacement of the perimeter with a small increase of tension. Springs with a very low elastic tension need to be elongated more than usual to produce the force required for proper conservation. They therefore allow a certain amount of displacement of the painting before it reaches dangerous stresses, thus offering a good degree of protection. **A.I.I.**

DESIGN OF SUPPORTS FOR DOUBLE-SIDED PAINTINGS

The design of supports for double-sided paintings generally poses challenging structural and aesthetic problems. From a structural point of view, rigidity is the most important characteristic: the support, reduced to its essence and being limited to a perimeter, must be self-supporting and non-deformable; this property is particularly important in the case of large format paintings and in the case of an elastic tension which stresses the supports constantly and in a visible way. The support cannot be hidden and therefore, from an aesthetic point of view, there is a need for harmonization and proportioning with the painting it is to be added to. At the same time, the support must accommodate and conceal the technological aspects of the mounting and tensioning system. At any rate, in the realization of the structures, a proper choice of materials is fundamental. Wood, despite its excellent qualities (high-performance efficiency, physical and technological properties, availability and, above all, low cost) would not be the best choice in the case of large paintings: the continuous stress imposed by the elastic tension over time can induce permanent deformations of the structure due to creeping, a visco-plastic slipping under mechanical stress. Enlarging the section of the structures or using woods with superior mechanical characteristics inevitably lead to an increase in weight. In large paintings, the solution is therefore represented by aluminum thanks to its high performance combined with dimensional stability; unfortunately, occasionally the development of appropriate aesthetic solutions cancels out the advantages in terms of weight

5. The double-sided banner from the Scrovegni Chapel in Padua mounted on its composite support; the frame is open, revealing the tensioning system.

when using this material. Where lightness and rigidity are required, a valid alternative may be represented by composite materials, systems consisting of two or more elements whose properties and performance are used in a way which offers superior characteristics to those of the constituents used individually. Composites, however, require a different design approach: the material is built according to its use with the aim of optimizing its technological, physical, mechanical, aesthetic and even economic aspects. Wood too can become a composite, by assembling different types whose best features are exploited to the maximum: a sandwich with two external skins of oak (chosen for its high elastic modulus) and a thick inner core of balsa end-grain (light and very resistant to cutting stress) create a rigid and light composite material. With fiber-reinforced plastics (e.g., composites consisting of carbon and epoxy), creative freedom in making shapes becomes absolute, in association with lightness, rigidity, and dimensional stability.

As an example, illustrated here is a support made recently for a double-sided banner (fig. 5) from the Scrovegni Chapel in Padova (activity carried out for the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro; intervention by Dr. Carla Zaccheo). The artifact, made of painted red silk, is very fragile and

6. Schematic section of the support made for the double-sided banner from the Scrovegni Chapel in Padua.

requires a delicate tension that can be precisely adjusted and calibrated. An ultra-lightweight composite double shell/frame was made for this banner to simplify handling operations. Each shell has a rigid sandwich structure with two carbon and epoxy skins and a PET core. A wood finish gives the support a traditional look (fig. 6). As always in our supports, this banner is tensioned by mechanical devices with long and soft springs (fig. 7); these devices have been designed to occupy little space, so that they can easily adapt to different technical solutions for new structures, or when reusing original or old frames. The support is completed by two rigid panels to be mounted on the composite shells to support the painting during transport and handling and prevent any dangerous effects of oscillations and vibrations. The panels, made of acid-free honeycomb cardboard, are held in place when needed by methacrylate brackets and magnets hidden in the composite shells (fig. 8). To conclude, it should also be noted that the mounting system illustrated has also been used for single-sided paintings, for example, in the case of artifacts without nailed edges, or those originally attached directly to the face of wooden stretchers and supports. The tensioning proves to be extremely efficient thanks to reduced friction while still remaining soft and gentle. **C.S.**

7. Detail of the tensioning system of the support made for the double-sided banner from the Scrovegni Chapel in Padua.

8. The double-sided banner from the Scrovegni Chapel in Padua gently enclosed, front and back, between two acid-free honeycomb cardboard panels for handling and transportation.

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Notes

¹ The test was performed with a biaxial tensile tester built by Antonio Iaccarino Idelson and Miguel Sanchez (Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain), within the PhD research conducted by Antonio Iaccarino Idelson at the Delft University of Technology under the supervision of Roger Groves, on cruciform samples measuring 25 mm x 25 mm (the arms of the cross are used only for clamping purposes). The canvas is a pure linen used for painting and

lining, 12 threads/cm in weft, 13 threads/cm in warp, 260 g/m², 0,4 mm thick. Rabbit skin glue in 10% solution (0,3 ml for the 6,25 cm² of the sample); environment at 50% RH and 23°C during the entire process. The test was performed on 5 samples of linen canvas with the following average numbers: pretensioned at 2 N/cm, stabilized for 20 minutes, when they reach 1,81 N/cm in warp 1,75 N/cm in weft; upon wetting, increase of tension up to 3,1 N/cm in warp and 2,8 N/cm in weft; with

water evaporation tension drops to 0,4 N/cm in warp and 0,5 N/cm in weft; further evaporation sees glue contraction, with an increase of tension 1,8 N/cm in warp and 2,4 N/cm in weft, when equilibrium is reached with the environmental moisture, 50% RH.

² This is of course an over-simplification, as we know from Marion Mecklenburg that also oil-based layers, especially when containing clay-based colors, have a similar behavior.

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Notes

¹ The research project by Federica Cerasi, Alessandra Ferlito and Giorgia Pinto ended in 2009 with the discussion of the degree thesis at the ISCR [Istituto Superiore per la Conservazione e il Restauro] entitled *The Banner of John the Baptist from Città di Castello. A comparative study of adhesives for a new approach to suturing lacerations and cuts*. The results of the experimentation were published in Cerasi, Ferlito, Pinto 2012.

² In 1952, 1983 and 2006.

³ The 2018 intervention was published in Vv.Aa. 2019.

⁴ Major studies on this topic include those by Berger, Russel 2000; Heiber 2002; Heiber, Demuth 2004; Knight, Pastorello 1994; Landi 2008.

⁵ Berger 2003; Scicolone 1990; Heiber 2003.

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⁶ The adhesives tested were: Paraloid B72, Plextol B500, Akeogard T40, Textile Superattak Gel, and Saldatutto. For the dilution percentages, see F. Cerasi *et al.* 2012.

⁷ Klucel M, TYLOSE MH 1000, TYLOSE MH300 ethers were selected and tested.

⁸ The tension delivered corresponds to about one and a half times the stress exerted by the weight of the banner alone along the upper edge (see Iaccarino Idelson *et al.* 2001).

⁹ Sutures made with Paraloid B72, epoxy resins and cyanoacrylates lost their mechanical properties with ageing, while polyurethane emulsions were poorly resistant to microbial attack.

¹⁰ One kilogram per linear centimetre, calculated on specimens with through-cut sutures, non-

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aged adhesive on linen cloth subjected to an ageing equivalent to approximately 400 years.

¹¹ The restoration was carried out by F. Cerasi, A. Ferlito, G. Pinto; *Lo stendardo di San Giovanni Battista a Città di Castello...* was published in 2011.

¹² The adhesive was applied at 8% in demineralized water.

¹³ The Atlas was promoted by A. M. Marcone and produced by F. Cerasi, A. Ferlito, G. Pinto; with the related charts and synoptic tables it constitutes a volume attached to the thesis *Lo stendardo di San Giovanni Battista a Città di Castello. Studio comparato di adesivi per un nuovo approccio alla sutura di lacerazioni e tagli*, 2009.

¹⁴ Published in Zaccheo, Cerasi, Giuliani, Arcangeli, Borgioli 2020.

¹⁵ Arcangeli, Borgioli 2015-16.

PART 2

Session 2

Mechanical properties and stretching of double-sided paintings

A quantitative review of tensions affecting tear repair decisions

Figure 1 compares all the different tensions discussed during the webinar. The vertical scale is logarithmic, four orders of magnitude. I will discuss the graphs from left to right.

Tension in a Restrained Painting as RH Changes: I selected examples from my compilation in Daly Hartin *et al.* (2021). If we select 30% RH as a climate that we want repairs to survive, then the range of tension is shown by the horizontal blue band: (0.3-0.6) kN/m. Paintings with thicker paints or heavy size will cause higher tensions, but this band is a reasonable benchmark.

Tension vs Deflection: Idelson (2009) proposed a Maximum Useful Tension (MUT) of 2-2.5 N/cm based on a study of paintings at different pre-tension. He pushed the centre of the painting with 8N (82g) and measured deflection (heavy black line) (Idelson 2021). The other lines are calculations for a 1m x 1m painting. The red lines are the change in sag of a painting held horizontally as pre-tension changes, for 400µm and 800µm thick paint. The green line is for a vertical painting facing a moderate wind (28 km/h). The transitions are all in the same region as Idelson's transition, but his deflections do not drop as rapidly. Milosovic (2016) has shown that point loads at the centre deflect a membrane much more than uniform loads. Local deformation occurs, like sticking your finger in a balloon. Still, the conclusion is the same – above -0.25 kN/m, more tension provides diminishing benefits. The red dots are for the sag and the tension in a painting (zero pre-tension) when horizontal. Deflection changes little as paint layers double, but tension doubles. Still, unless the paints are very thick, tension remains

below that of low RH. [Technical: The line plots were generated using Excel's solver on the equation for a prestressed membrane by Hermida (1999). Red dots used equations for a membrane in Maddux *et al.* (1969) Paint and ground density calculated at 40%PVC, oil SG 1.3, pigment set at an average of lead white (SG 6.6) and inorganic pigments (SG 3.5). Canvas 200 g/m². Elasticity (E) set at 1GPa, typical of 10s events in pigmented media that approach glassy phase. Stress strain plots for 14 years-old lead white (Mecklenberg, 2021) give E= 0.4 GPa at small strain, but were made over several weeks. Adjusted by the viscoelastic master curve by Daly Hartin *et al.* (2015) which gives a ratio of 0.45 between a month-long test and a 10s test.

Tension Due to Weight When Hanging: (same canvas weight and paint densities as the previous paragraph). The curves show three total thicknesses of paint. A tension/weight scale is provided in kg/m, e.g., a heavy painting, 1600 µm of paint (triple line), 2m long, will experience 5 kg/m (0.05 kN/m) at the top, and weighs 5kg for each meter of width. Even at 4m, these tensions are far below that caused by 30% RH on a restrained painting.

Tension at Break of Linen, Paper, Consolidant: At the top, brown squares for strength of naturally aged canvas (Hackney and Hedley 1981). Data on individual threads converted to an estimate for canvas by using the thread count of 39 per inch. Strength dropped by 30% in 24 years for the sample exposed to open air. In terms of exponential decay, this is ½ each 50 years, 1/8 after 150 years, so 5 kN/m. This is less than that of acid+heat aged canvas used for treatment tests by Peacock (1983) and by Bohme *et al.* (2020) both near 8 kN/m. It would drop to 0.01 kN/m at 600 years. But Peacock measured ancient Egyptian linen at 1.6 kN/m. As with paper, the key is pH. Centuries old canvas ranges from robust to powder. Bohme's (2020) study of consolidants in aged cotton canvas (brown diamonds) showed only 10% by weight of canvas could add 0.8 –2.2 kN/m to strength. This can be enough to get just above the blue band of tension due to 30%RH. Hopeful. Red crosses are based on individual flax fibre data by Soatthiyanon *et al.* (2015) plus the diameter of medium fibres, 26 µm. (Rahman *et al.*, 2013). Even just 100 bridging fibres/cm, can get above the blue band of RH tension, e.g. 15 threads/cm need 7 fibres per thread. At 450 fibres/cm, one is far above the blue band. A composite of flax and resin can be so strong that a 0.1mm layer reaches 10kN/m strength. Hopeful. Paper

bridges are common treatments. The grey bar shows the strengths of thin Japanese papers made of kozo (Nicholson and Page 1988) which rise above the blue band.

Tension at Break of Various Bonds: Data from Demuth and Flock (2021) is important because they measured many replicates, so variance can be studied. This goes to the heart of user's risk assessment of thread repair: how consistent (reliable) are such bonds? I collapsed the data into the dominant factor: the four types of joint. Adhesive mixtures with starch paste were excluded since they were significantly weaker than all others. The red boxes show the range in average strength across adhesives. The strength obviously climbs from left to right. The blue bars show the highest and lowest single samples. This indicates the variance even an expert user can expect, as much as $\pm\frac{1}{2}$ the average. The second and fourth types are more consistent, more reliable geometries. Still, even the butt joints are above the blue band most of the time, and the three reinforced geometries are double or more the top of the band, 4 times higher if the painting is not incorrectly keyed out at mid RH. Overlap+fibres approaches the performance of the industrial flax+resin composite of 0.1mm. The other two studies found butt joints four times weaker. Butt joints by Fontana et al (2021) fall below the blue band and even below MUT. I have not labelled the individual adhesives in the study by Cerasi *et al.* (2012), my purpose is to show the lack of any clear pattern across the four categories of Ageing, as well to show the wide variance (reported as standard deviations). The single exception is the adhesive a hot-melt powder, "TEXTILE". It is comparable to the best of Demuth and Flock before ageing, as well as very consistent (small variance).

In summary, successful butt joints can achieve strengths well above a stringent target of tension due to 30% RH. They can be far stronger than the cautious tension of MUT. In a restrained painting, if one is pessimistic about the strength of unreinforced butt joints, then either loosen the frame, or stabilize the RH with a closed microenvironment. A spring-loaded stretcher set below MUT will work in theory but I have not yet seen proof of operation. Tension due to the paintings own weight when hanging, or when held horizontally by a stretcher, or blowing in a breeze, does not threaten repairs unless size and thickness become extreme. Consolidant must enter the yarn capillaries as well as fill the joint.

1. Tension in paintings from various causes. The vertical scale is logarithmic, four orders of magnitude. The preferred SI scale is kN/m, which is within 2% of kg/cm. Some authors use N/cm. For US colleagues, lb/in is provided.

It must not be notched by a meniscus on curing. The key element for success is rapid control of viscosity – low enough initially to enter the yarn capillaries, then quickly high enough not to “starve” the joint. The process is more like soldering than glueing. Hence the success of hot melts. Gelatins (and animal glues) might succeed, but must be manipulated so as not to gel until after penetration but then to quickly gel before joint starvation. Unfortunately, they still lose a lot of volume on drying. The addition of fibres achieves two benefits: fibres are much stronger than most consolidants (if bonded to each other), and as a matrix they can hold the consolidant as it sets. Bridges or overlaps reinforce this effect, and prevent stress concentration, the root cause of any fracture.

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An introduction to mechanics and the Giulio Cesare Procaccini double-sided banner

INTRODUCTION

Having never personally seen the painting, I was heavily dependent on the comprehensive photographic and scientific analyses graciously provide to me by the banner researchers and organizers of the Venaria conference held in November 2020¹. The results of that research made it possible to draw some conclusions about the current condition of the banner and suggest some possible treatment options. There were three basic questions I wanted to address. 1, how did the banner get to the condition that it is in, 2, how does such a banner possibly respond structurally to environmental changes and 3, are spring loaded stretchers effective in reducing the forces and stresses in treated banner? Figure 1 shows the image of the better-preserved side of the banner.

MATERIALS USED IN THE BANNER

First off, the technical information I have received suggests the presence of a glue size and that size would be on both sides of the canvas. Further, “The ground and paint layers are applied on both sides of the canvas. The numerous abrasions of the paint layer allowed the observation of a reddish-brown ground, later identified by the cross-section analysis. The ground layers are made of a mixture of earth pigments and ochre with calcium carbonate or calcium sulphate. The thickness of the paint layers is varied, but it can generally be considered significant given the type of artwork: banners were usually made with light materials (silk support and very thin paint layers with no ground)”². Further in the same article the paint layers are identifies as: FLESH-TONES lead white, cinnabar and earth pigment

1. Giulio Cesare Procaccini, *Madonna con Bambino, San Pietro, San Giovannino e Angeli* (back), Milan, Pinacoteca di Brera, before the conservation treatment.

WHITE lead white
 RED vermilion
 PURPLE cinnabar, madder lake, lead white
 YELLOW lead tin yellow, ochre and earth pigments
 GREEN copper green or malachite, copper resinate
 BLUE azurite, smalt³.

INTRODUCTION TO MECHANICS

At this point it would be useful to present a quick introduction to the mechanical properties of oil paints and the factors that influence those properties. One of those factors that must be considered are the pigments used in making the paint. Another

2. Basic stress strain plot of a 14-25-year-old lead white paint. The same figure shows the yield point where the paint transitions from elastic (fully reversible) to plastic (non-reversible). In the plastic region the paint is permanently deformed.

3. Basic stress strain plot of a 14-25-year-old lead white paint at different levels of relative humidity and temperatures. Low RH stiffens the paint and low temperature makes the paint become brittle.

4. Stress-strain plots of lead white ground in cold pressed linseed oil at different stages of drying. The older this paint gets, the stiffer and stronger it gets (the stress when the paint film breaks). However paints made with most pigments don't develop the strengths shown.

is relative humidity and temperature. Stress can be loosely considered a force per unit area and strain is the elongation (stretching) per unit length. Figure 2 shows the basic stress strain plot of a 14-25-year-old lead white paint. The same figure shows

the yield point where the paint transitions from elastic (fully reversible) to plastic (non-reversible). In the plastic region the paint is permanently deformed. The end of test is where the paint breaks. Figure 3 shows the basic stress strain plot of a 14-25-year-old lead white paint at different levels of relative humidity and temperatures. Low RH stiffens the paint and low temperature makes the paint become brittle.

These types of tests help us understand how paints dry and how the environment influences them. Figure 4 shows the stress-strain plots of lead white ground in cold pressed linseed oil at different stages of drying. The older this paint gets, the stiffer and stronger it gets (the stress when the paint film breaks). However, paints made with most pigments don't develop the strength shown below (figs. 2-4).

HYDROLYSIS OF PAINT

This section of this discussion is important. Hydrolysis is moisture attacking and weakening nearly all paint films to one degree or another. It is particularly aggressive in deteriorating the earth colors and at high humidity environments. This includes yellow ochre, raw and burnt umber, raw and burnt sienna, and iron oxide. Hydrolysis also severely attacks oil paints containing organic pigments⁴. This is the results of the fundamental drying mechanism that results in either a durable or weak film. Figure 5 shows the stress-strain plots of raw umber ground in cold pressed linseed oil after 7.5 years and 12 years of drying. Of interest here is that the paint has nearly all strength at 14 years of drying. This was the result of hydrolysis of the paint even though this paint was confined to a "museum environment". This effect has been to be shown in paints made with rea umber, burnt and raw sienna, iron oxide and yellow ochre. These paints are typical of those found in the banner (fig. 5).

In addition, there are grounds made with certain pigments that might be called "inert pigments" and mixed in drying oils. These include silica, barium sulfate, and calcium carbonate and never really dry to firm films. Calcium carbonate is found in the grounds of the banner. Figure 6 shows the stress-strain plots for silica ground in cold pressed linseed oil, and linseed with litharge, barium sulfate and calcium carbonate ground in cold pressed linseed oil, and for comparison to a durable paint, basic lead carbonate in cold pressed linseed oil. The paints made with the silica, barium sulphate, and calcium carbonate have no strength at all. The plot with the lead white paint is shown to illustrate the

5. Stress-strain plots of raw umber ground in cold pressed linseed oil after 7.5 years and 14 years of drying. Of interest here is that the paint has lost nearly all strength at 14 years of drying. This was the result of hydrolysis of the paint even though this paint was confined to a "museum environment".

6. Shows the stress-strain plots silica ground in cold pressed linseed oil, and linseed with litharge, barium sulfate and calcium carbonate ground in cold pressed linseed oil, and for comparison to a durable paint, basic lead carbonate in cold pressed linseed oil.

dramatic differences in a durable paint and those made with the "inert pigments" (fig. 6).

Let's pause here and summarize a bit. Unless stabilized by other means, the earth colors hydrolyze over time, deteriorate, and lose strength⁵. In addition, the earth colors, especially when deteriorated, gain and lose considerable moisture, as such they swell and shrink with increases and decreases of ambient RH. If the RH gets high, above 70%, the swelling is extreme. Conversely, oil paints made with or mixed with lead white in linseed oil get stronger and stiffer with time and are extremely resistant to moisture. As such they can resist adverse environmental condition fairly well. The Procaccini painted banner contains many of the paints described above.

HOW WOULD A STRETCHED (RESTRAINED) BANNER RESPOND TO CHANGES IN RH?

Let's explore the possibilities. We can conduct the restrained experiments on the individual layers found in typical paintings or banners. By doing so it is possible to determine how each layer of a painting (and the painting as a whole) or the banner responds to the environment.

First let's look at a more recent painting. Suppose we cut a strip out of the central section of the painting and completely restrain it as if it were stretched on a stretcher. Then we will change the relative humidity (RH). Because of the restraint and the materials capacity to swell and shrink, forces will develop or relax as a result of the changing RH in each of the layers of the painting. While all of the materials in paintings develop forces, it is the hide glue that is the most responsive. Figures 7a and b compare forces of the materials of a model painting restrained and subjected to changes

7 a, b. Comparison the materials of a model of a restrained and desiccated painting to the theoretical model of a restrained and desiccated double-sided banner.

8 a, b. Comparison the theoretical restrained response of the double-sided banner to a model lined painting. Lined painting data courtesy of Cecil K. Andersen.

in RH to the theoretical model of a double-sided banner. It is the added layer of glue size in the double-sided banner that increases the forces developed. For comparison purposes the banner plots show the force development in a hypothetically degraded glue (fig. 7a-b).

Just as an aside, it is worth pointing out that the double-sided banner (glue size on both sides of the canvas) behaves in a very similar fashion as a glue-paste lined painting (one layer of size on one side of the canvas and a glue-paste layer on the other). So whatever support decisions are made they pretty much hold for both types of paintings. Figures 8a and b compare the theoretical restrained response of the double-sided banner to a model lined painting. The total forces developed at both low and high RH in each case is very similar (fig. 8a-b).

SOME THOUGHTS ABOUT SPRING LOADED STRETCHERS

Let's take a strip of a painting and attach one end to a spring with a spring constant, K. Now let's attach the free end of the painting strip and the free end of the spring to fixed supports and change the RH. In Figure 9, the plot labeled "full restraint" shows the summation of all of the forces from the materials shown in figure 7a. This represents a condition where the "attached spring" has an infinitely high spring constant, K or no ability to stretch. The maximum force level is about 4.4 N/cm and this level of force is nearly the same for all glue sized paintings (see the unlined primed canvas plot in Figure 8b). At the other extreme in figure 9 is the bottom plot labeled "no restraint" and this represents the condition where the strip of a painting is free to expand and contract with changes in RH. In this case the "attached spring" has a spring constant $K = 0$ (zero). Consequently, there is no force developed. Now let's look at the plots in between the extremes discussed above and labeled K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 . If a spring with any value of K in between the extremes is used the effect will be as follows. If the RH is decreased, the painting will contract as the spring expands. While the force in the spring increases the total force in the painting will also increase but less than if it were fully restrained because the spring is allowing the painting strip to relax (or contract) a bit and the force in the spring and painting strip (the system) will be equal. The intermediate plots of the painting strip attached to spring with decreasing spring constants are shown in figure 9 also. There are some caveats however. With a changing RH, a fully restrained painting will experience the minimum structural interaction between layers where the lack of restraint induces the maximum interaction between the painting's

layers. This means that at high RH an unrestrained painting might experience paint cleavage at high RH levels. Further analysis is needed to determine the optimum spring constants for individual paintings. In general, spring-loaded stretchers don't negate the need to maintain a moderate ambient environment (fig. 9).

LOOKING AT AN ACTUAL APPLICATION OF SPRING-LOADED STRETCHERS

The real question I had while listening to the talks at the Venaria conference was how much force was being applied by the springs to the banner? Antonio Iaccarino was most gracious to send me his talk that had actual measured loading data near 50% RH. It was in the units of kilograms per meter of the painting's edge which I converted into Newtons per cm of the painting's edge. Below are the load ranges for lined and unlined paintings⁶.

9. Hypothetical effects of spring-loaded stretchers on paintings.

10 a, b. The Iccarino data falls within the safe areas of a simple painting, a hypothetical banner and a lined painting.

Type	Kg/M	N/cm
Unlined	8	0.784
Unlined	16	1.569
Lined	14	1.372
Lined	24	2.353

I found the load comparison remarkable in that Antonio's data fall safely within the load results I found in measuring actual paintings and their materials. Figures 10a and b show the Iaccarino data falls within the safe areas of a simple painting, a hypothetical banner, and a lined painting (fig. 10a-b).

SOME CONCLUSIONS

Studying the mechanical (and chemical) properties of cultural materials will help understand degradation processes in banners and easel paintings.

Mechanics can help determine the effects of both RH (and temperature) and the forces throughout the painting materials. The "spring loaded stretchers" hold considerable promise and I highly recommend further research in their development and use. I think that there are other considerations such as non-uniform distribution of forces in the paintings that should be considered.

Notes

¹ Caterina Fontana 2016-2017; Technical Dossier arranged by CCR, 2020. With the project "Structural treatments on double-sided paintings" the Centro Conservazione e Restauro La Venaria Reale (CCR) joined "Conserving Canvas", an international grant initiative funded by the Getty Foundation and focused on projects concerning the conservation of canvas paintings.

² Technical Dossier arranged by CCR, 2020.

³ *Ibidem*.

⁴ Erhardt, Tumosa, Mecklenburg 2005b; Mecklenburg, Tumosa, Erhardt 2005a.

⁵ Mecklenburg, Tumosa, Vicenzi 2013.

⁶ See the paper by Antonio Iaccarino Idelson and Carlo Serino in this volume.

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